

TABLE I—CYANOETHYLATION OF CYANOACETANILIDES TO α , CYANO α , α -BIS-(β -CYANOETHYL) ACETANILIDES

(R)	M.P. °C	Yield	Mol. formula	Carbon		Hydrogen		Nitrogen	
				F	R	F	R	F	R
4-Cl	155	75	C ₁₅ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl	59.10	59.90	40.30	40.30	18.54	18.63
2-Cl	104-05	85	C ₁₅ H ₉ ON ₄ Cl	59.91	59.9	40.34	40.32	18.71	18.63
4-CH ₃	260-62	60	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₄	62.12	67.1	5.71	5.70	20.0	20.0
3-CH ₃	248-49	65	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₄	67.14	67.1	5.71	5.70	20.1	20.0
4-OCH ₃	215-17	50	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₄	64.90	64.87	5.41	5.40	18.73	18.90
3-r	248	60	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ N ₄ BrO	52.2	52.17	3.81	3.77	16.18	16.23
4-NO ₂	208-10	80	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.9	57.67	4.17	4.18	22.42	22.50
3-NO ₂	85-86	55	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.89	57.87	4.2	4.18	22.45	22.50
2-NO ₂	205-06	50	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₅ O ₄	57.89	57.87	4.21	4.18	22.52	22.50

cooling. The stirring was continued for 5 hours 30-35°. The solution was neutralised with dil. hydrochloric acid and poured into ice water. The solid thus separated was recrystallized from ethanol into colourless crystals, m.p. 150°; yield, 2.8g (40%). Found N, 20.97%; C, 67.86%; H, 5.20%. C₁₅H₉N₄O required, N, 21.05%; C, 67.67%; H, 5.20%.

Similarly other substituted cyanoacetanilides were prepared by the above method. They are given in table I.

Results and Discussion

Only five compounds were tested in α cyano- α , α -bis(β -cyanoethyl, acetanilide series. They did not show any significant insecticidal activity on adult housefly. A comparative study of the insecticidal activity of these cyanoethylated cyanoacetanilides, malonanilides, ethyl malonates and their derivatives will be described elsewhere.

Acknowledgements

The author wishes to thank Dr. Nitya Anand Director, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and Tata Pesticides Division, Bangalore for analysis and biological activity of the compounds respectively.

References

- G. S. MISRA and J. S. SHUKLA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 29, 455.
- J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1965, 3, 572.
- J. S. SHUKLA and R. K. SRIVASTAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 375.

Heteropoly-Niobate and Tantalate Containing Vanadium(V)

SALIL KUMAR ROY and H. C. MISHRA

University Department of Chemistry, Ranchi University, Ranchi-834 008

Manuscript received 5 August 1976, revised 1 December 1976, accepted 30 December 1976

THE present communication deals with the preparation and characterisation of two new heteropoly salts of niobium and tantalum containing vanadium as the hetero atom. Previous reports^{1,2} on such studies are only a few.

Aqueous solutions of freshly prepared³ and analysed potassium hexaniobate, K₇HNb₆O₁₉·13H₂O, and potassium metavanadate were taken in the molar ratio of 12 : 1 and refluxed for 6 hr. in a round bottom flask provided with a series of potash bulb guard tubes which absorbed CO₂ from air. Thus hydrolysis of alkali metal hexaniobate, due to the presence of atmospheric CO₂, was easily avoided. The refluxed solution was then left in atmosphere for three days and finally crystallised under vacuum when light yellow needle shaped crystals came out which were recrystallised thrice from hot water. For analysis of the compound, vanadium was estimated colorimetrically by hydrogen peroxide method⁴. Niobium was estimated gravimetrically⁵ by precipitating it as niobic acid with conc. HCl and then weighing as Nb₂O₅ at 850°. Hydrogen was estimated by element estimation technique (Found: K, 15.32; V, 1.97; Nb, 44.27; H, 1.59 percent. Calcd. for K₁₂H [VNB₁₂O₄₈]20H₂O : K, 15.44; V, 2.01; Nb, 44.15; H, 1.61 percent). The final representation

of the formula was according to the views suggested by Lindqvist⁶ for complex heteropoly anion $[X^n + Nb_{12}O_{38}]^{(16-n)-}$.

X-ray Crystallographic Data—From rotation and equi-inclination Weissenberg X-ray diffraction photographs for a single crystal of the compound, the values of cell parameters were analysed to be $a=15.66$, $b=26.10$, $c=8.40$ Å and $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$, hence the system is orthorhombic. The volume V per unit cell was calculated to be $3,433.298$ Å³. The space group was uniquely established to be $D_{2h}^{28}-P_{nnp}$. The number of molecules per unit cell 'z' was found to be 2. The observed density, measured by floatation method, $\rho_{obs.}=2.46$ gml⁻¹. From the relation $\rho_{obs.} = \frac{1.66 M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M' of the compound came to 2533 against the theoretical molecular weight 2524.87, which definitely concludes that the compound is monomeric.

The corresponding heteropoly tantalatovanadate(V) has also been prepared successfully by the same method as described above for the preparation of potassium 12-niobovanadate(V). Here the starting materials were potassium vanadate and freshly prepared⁸ and analysed potassium hexatantalate. Light yellow needle shaped crystals of potassium 12-tantalatovanadate obtained, were crystallised from hot water. Tantalum in the compound was estimated gravimetrically⁵ as Ta_2O_5 . (Found : K, 8.50 ; V, 1.35 ; Ta, 60.15 ; H, 1.49%. Calcd. for $K_9H_3 [V Ta_{12}O_{38}] 26H_2O$: K, 8.63 ; V, 1.41 ; Ta, 60.08 ; H, 1.52%).

Crystallographic data : The crystal data of the compound were as follows : $a=16.56$, $b=35.12$, $c=14.72$ Å, $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$. The system is orthorhombic. Volume per unit cell = $8,560.963$ Å³. The space group was uniquely established to I_{41}/a . The number of molecules per unit cell 'Z' was found to be 4. $\rho_{obs.}$ came to 2.79 gml⁻¹. From the relation stated above, the molecular weight of the compound came to 3597 against the theoretically calculated value 3612.5, hence the compound is a monomer.

Several attempts were made to prepare a corresponding mixed 12-niobotantalatovanadate(V) anion without success.

References

1. W. B. DALE, J. M. BUCKLEY and M. T. POPE, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 2A, 301.
2. SALIL KUMAR ROY and G. C. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 52, 1151.
3. G. L. MILLER, 'Metallurgy of Rare Earth Metals—Tantalum and Niobium'. Butterworth Scientific Publications, London, 1959, Vol. VI, p. 68.
4. F. D. SNELL and C. T. SNELL, 'Colorimetric Analysis'. D. Van Nostrand Company Inc, 1966, p. 110.
5. W. WILFRED SCOTT and N. HOWELL FURMAN, 'Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis', Technical Press Ltd., London, 1958, P. 871, 875.
6. I. LINDQVIST, *Ark. Kemi*, 1953, 5, 247 ; 1954, 7, 49.